

ANALYSIS OF INDONESIA'S ECONOMY PREPARATION IN FACING ICT MASTERPLAN 2020

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Abstract.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) on economic performance has becoming an interesting issue in the field of economics. Strong economic growth, well educated population, as well as the rapid development of information and communication technology (ICT) sectors, are the primary drivers of ASEAN's digital economy as a community, including for Indonesia. Some previous data indicated that the growth and development of the internet in Indonesia is still not in accordance with what is expected, including in supporting the development of business. Therefore, it should be noted how the impact of ICT Master Plan 2020 implementation for Indonesia in order to develop a good implementation strategy that is appropriate with the Indonesian economy so that Indonesia can face the implementation of ICT Master Plan 2020 with a successful result. This paper is done by literature review approach. The method used is descriptive. The findings show that Indonesia is well prepared to face the ICT Master Plan 2020 with various plans that have been prepared until 2020 and this begins with changing workplace and economic structure that brings the impact of economic and technological developments in the current era of digital economy, not only increase productivity and growth, but also serve as a foundation for the remote urban and rural communities in Indonesia.

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1. Introduction

In the face of the Asean Economic Community (AEC), ten countries in Southeast Asia that are members of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) must have preparations in various sectors, without exception Information Technology (IT), especially regarding the implementation of e-ASEAN. The great vision of the ASEAN economic community in realizing ASEAN integration must be supported by various aspects, one of which is the progress of the ICT (Information and Communication Technology) system. ICT is fundamental in supporting trading activities because it can open communication spaces and trade transactions through e-commerce, facilitate investment, expand markets through its ability to provide information exchange facilities, facilitate marketing through online advertisements, facilitate innovation through the exchange of information and ideas, communication costs which is cheaper, creates credibility towards the ability to use ICT so that it attracts investors to invest. This is fundamental because the leaders of ASEAN countries are aware of the benefits obtained if ICT is one of the important instruments.

ICT Masterplan, first launched in 2011 namely ASEAN ICT Masterplan 2011-2015. The ICT Masterplan 2015 contains the main ICT development plans in the ASEAN region between 2011 and 2015, then the ICT Masterplan 2020 was launched. In the ASEAN ICT Ministers Meeting in Da Nang, Vietnam, all ministers of communication and information technology in Southeast Asia agreed to adopt ASEAN ICT Masterplan 2020. The development of the ASEAN ICT Masterplan

2020 is focused on enabling large economic transformations. Then explained also there are 3 additional points on the previous master plan. This is to address the dynamics that occur in the rapidly changing ICT industry. Additional issues are ICT in the single market, new media and content, information security and assurance. The vision for ICT Masterplan 2020 is to encourage ASEAN to digital to enable a safe, sustainable and transformative economy, and to enable an innovative, inclusive and integrated ASEAN community. ICT will be used to support digital inclusion and social equality, where marginalized, under-preserved and vulnerable communities have a way to engage and enter the digital economy. Future generation of ICT applications is a trigger for good growth. The impact of the ICT Master plan was also felt in Indonesia. This caused the development and progress of information and communication technology (ICT) to be very good and felt in almost every aspect of people's lives. Not only feel the impact but Indonesia needs to support and succeed ICT Masterplan 2020 especially in the economic field which is often referred to as the digital economy. In Indonesia the role of the digital economy in world economic growth will be increasingly significant. The Ministry of Communication and Informatics (Kemenkominfo) projects that by 2020, the digital economy in Indonesia can grow to 130 billion US dollars or Rp 1,700 trillion (exchange rate of Rp. 13,333 per US dollar). The 2020 digital economy projection figure is estimated at 20 percent of the total GDP (Gross Domestic Product) of Indonesia. The Minister of Communication and Information Technology (Kemenkominfo) explained to achieve this digital economic projection Indonesia must be truly mature so that the vision of Indonesia as the largest digital economy in Southeast Asia in 2020 and at the same time accelerate the economic growth of the Indonesian people in the digital era can be realized. Therefore, Indonesia's readiness in facing the ICT Masterplan 2020 must be truly organized especially in the economic field.

2. Research Methodology

The writing of this article was conducted to find out how much the Indonesian economy is prepared to face the ICT Masterplan 2020, so that critical theory studies will be used, the application of which will be carried out through descriptive analysis. Descriptive research method is a method that attempts to describe, interpret something, for example conditions or relationships that exist, opinions that develop, the ongoing process, the effects or effects that occur or about the ongoing trend. In accordance with the approach used in this study, the data used is taken from articles from trusted scientific journals, applicable regulations, and relevant statements. Thus the analytical technique used is the analytical technique that is carried out is an analysis technique (Content analysis).

3. Results and Discussion

The discussion about ICT Masterplan 2020 must be understood as one of the instruments that are important for the life of the Indonesian state. Before deeper understanding of the ICT Master Plan 2020 needs to be understood in advance the current Indonesian economic conditions. As a large country, both in terms of area and population, it turns out that Indonesia is not a large country in terms of economy. Indonesia is only ranked 7th in Asia, or ranked 26th in the world (Microsoft Encarta Weltatlas, 2001). Such a situation is inseparable from its short relative economic history, complete with problems that still surround it to this day. From 1971 - 1981 Indonesia recorded

consistent and very impressive economic growth (above 5 percent per year). However, as the price of oil began to fall around the beginning of 1982 (to only around US \$ 10 per barrel), Indonesia's economic growth rate also went (less than 5 percent per year). In 1998 the Indonesian economy experienced a negative growth of around 12.5 percent. The value of the currency dropped around 80 percent, while the stock exchange dropped more than 50 percent. In addition, dozens of industries were forced to close due to lack of raw materials which resulted in extraordinary unemployment. Therefore, it is understandable that in the end almost all industries almost died when the financial crisis hit Indonesia in 1997. The fall of the rupiah caused our industry to experience a scarcity of raw materials that could no longer be imported. On the contrary, the conglomerates of capital owners prefer to run their funds abroad, resulting in massive capital outflows. In addition, the debts of the conglomerates (which were later converted to public debt during the administration of President Habibie), eventually dragged Indonesia into a prolonged financial crisis to date. In conditions that are still "sick" and with an extraordinary debt burden like today, our economy is still being hit by the current of globalization that requires Indonesia to follow the development of the era. Indonesia is experiencing economic growth at the latest in the last five years. But in the digital era, the growth of the e-commerce industry which is part of the digital economy is even more rapid amid the slowing pace of the country's economy. Predicted by 2020, the volume of commerce business in Indonesia can reach USD 130 billion, equivalent to IDR 1,714 trillion, not a number that deserves to be ignored. So that there is hope that the e-commerce industry can become one of the backbones of the economy. To achieve these targets, a road map is needed to open access to various business sectors to enter, join and strengthen the building of digital economic ecosystems. One of them is by knowing the potential of digital economic growth in Indonesia. This is important for the formulation of government policies that are closely related to the digital industry sector in the present and future. And this digital economy is one of the important tools for Indonesia's economic readiness in facing the ICT Masterplan 2020. The role of the digital economy in world economic growth will be increasingly significant. To maximize this potential, the Indonesian government has provided various important things to support Indonesia's economic readiness in the face of the ICT Masterplan 2020, including:

3.1. Transformation of UMKM into e-UMKM

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are productive businesses owned by individuals or individual business entities that have annual sales of between 300 million to 50 billion rupiah (Law of the Republic of Indonesia, 2008). MSMEs have contributed to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of 57-60% with a labor absorption rate of around 97% of the total workforce in Indonesia (Indonesian Banking Development Institute and Bank Indonesia, 2015). MSMEs also proved to be unaffected by the economic crisis that hit Indonesia in 1997-1998. According to data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), the number of MSMEs has not decreased, increasing to absorb 85 million to 107 million workers by 2012 (Indonesian Central Bureau of Statistics, 2013). UMKM is the backbone of the populist economic system to reduce poverty and its development is able to expand the economic base and can contribute significantly in improving regional economy and national economic resilience. In order to win the competition in the free market, MSMEs must also develop in accordance with the times. Basically with the help of

Information and Communication Technology can improve performance so that it is more effective and efficient. So even though there is a slight difference in costs with traditional systems, MSMEs can enjoy facilities from IT that will provide the equivalent return to e-UMKM. With IT, MSMEs will be better prepared to compete not only domestically but also with foreign products. We can compete in terms of quality, packaging, and the speed of operations of the company and more importantly is in the marketing of MSME products. It is hoped that many new e-UMKMs will be created as a result of the transformation of MSME businesses in every region in Indonesia. The more and more massive e-UMKM that succeed and succeed in doing business online on the Internet, the stronger the national economy will be, because so far UMKM is the backbone of the country's economic strength.

3.2. Development of local startups in Indonesia.

Startup is no longer a foreign term for Indonesian people, especially in the business environment. The rapid development of startups is due to the rapid development of internet technology. According to data from an online media, there are currently at least more than 1,500 local startups operating in Indonesia and will continue to grow each year. However, the large number of startups that are born are also directly proportional to the number of startups that fall in their journey. Many factors are the reason for the failure of a number of startups. To overcome these various obstacles and minimize the risks faced by startups, incubator and accelerator programs are carried out. In Indonesia, there are already a number of incubator and accelerator programs that are ready to help the country's startup development. The Indonesian government through the Ministry of Communication and Information together with PT Kibar Kreasi Indonesia has also initiated the 1,000 National Movement of Digital Startup with the aim of producing quality startups and having a positive impact by resolving major problems in Indonesia. PT Kibar Kreasi Indonesia (Kibar) collaborates with Google to accommodate the community and strengthen the startup company's ecosystem in Indonesia. Kibar will also get access to the Google for Entrepreneurs Passport program. For Google, this partnership reinforces their commitment to helping Indonesia to become the country with the largest digital economy in Southeast Asia. This movement is targeted to create 1,000 new companies with a total business valuation of US \$ 10 billion by 2020.

3.3. Indonesia's Digital Economic Cooperation was developed

Indonesia with Australia hold the Indonesia-Australia Digital Forum (IADF) as a form of commitment of the two countries to collaborate in the digital economy. The Indonesia-Australia cooperation comes along with the development of the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) which is growing very rapidly and has become a staple of the world community. One of the uses of ICT is digital transformation aimed at improving digital economy. The Digital Forum initiated by Indonesia and Australia began with a meeting between Indonesian President Joko Widodo and Australian Prime Minister Malcolm Turnbull in 2017 in Sydney. Where one of the agreements that need to be followed up is the agreement on cooperation in the digital economy, namely to become a co-host of digital forum implementation in Indonesia. Both heads of state hope that this forum will enhance cooperation in the fields of technology, science, innovation and digital economy between Indonesia and Australia. The 2018 IADF is a commitment of Indonesia and Australia to collaborate in the digital economy. The 2018 IADF

lasts for two days from January 31 to February 1, 2018, with the theme "Share, Engage, Connect, Collaborate" and is expected to be an opportunity to improve and expand the cooperation between the Indonesian and Australian government and private sectors in the digital sector, as well as the means to add insight, creating new ideas and sharing best practices for various sector themes.

Then, Indonesia with Singapore President Joko Widodo agreed to a number of cooperation agreements with Singapore Prime Minister Lee Hsien Loong at The Istana, Singapore. One of the agreements reached is the development of the digital economy. By combining investment potential, technology with talent and huge market potential, the President believes that digital economic cooperation will bring Indonesia's and Singapore's economy to a greater leap forward. In addition to the digital economy, tourism cooperation is also a great opportunity that has not been optimized. Indonesia has a very complete tourism object, historical, cultural, natural, culinary or shopping. New destinations continue to be developed including Ten New Bali. With this potential, President Jokowi and PM Lee agreed to enhance cooperation and synergize the advantages of both countries in the field of tourism.

3.4. Adequate Infrastructure Development

The development of information technology infrastructure is the mainstay of the government in preparing a digital economic foundation. Coordinating Minister for Economic Affairs Darmin Nasution said that currently the foundation for the digital economy was being prepared. According to him, to reach the largest digital economy country in Southeast Asia there are at least some things that must be prepared. Minister of Industry Airlangga Hartarto revealed that the government was preparing various supporting infrastructure facilities to drive the digital economy through industrial bases and electronic commerce (e-commerce). According to him, the availability of infrastructure and mastery of information technology and communication are the main things in facing the development of the digital economy. The government has built infrastructure in the form of fiber optic network, Palapa Ring project, and enlarged bandwidth capacity. It is expected that the infrastructure can encourage acceleration of digital economic growth.

3.5. Human Resource Development

The government will prepare a curriculum to welcome the digital economy. This is to prepare human resources to compete in the digital era like today. President Joko Widodo said that later vocational high schools and colleges must have a department related to digital economics. In addition to the curriculum related to digital economics, it is expected that there will also be teaching materials about logistics, retail, e-commerce management and animation. Some of the curriculum will be prepared by the government in the future.

3.6. Security and Consumer Protection

Negative aspects of e-commerce development are related to security issues in transactions using e-commerce media. The emergence of fraud forms that tend to harm consumers and cause various legal problems in conducting e-commerce transactions. In trade transactions, consumers are absolutely required to be protected. The importance of legal protection for consumers is due to

the weak bargaining position of consumers. Legal protection for consumers requires partiality to weak bargaining positions (consumers). Legal protection for consumers is by protecting consumer rights. If consumers will truly be protected, then the rights of consumers must be fulfilled, both by the state and business actors, because the fulfillment of these consumer rights will protect consumers' losses from various aspects. Consumer protection in the digital economy era has become a serious concern of Indonesia by setting the standardization of SNI ISO / IEC 27001: 2013 as a requirement of the Standard Information Security Management System by determining the requirements for establishing, implementing, maintaining and continuously improving the Information Security Management System (ISMS) in organizational context. This standard also includes requirements for the assessment and handling of information security risks tailored to the needs of the organization. In addition, the government is working on a legal umbrella to ensure a security system, protection of user privacy and business competition in the digital and conventional world. The Head of the National Standardization Agency (BSN), Bambang Prasetya said, coinciding with the 40th International Session of ISO / COPOLCO (International Organization for Standardization / Committee on Consumer Policy) which took place on May 7-10, 2018. BSN in collaboration with ISO COPOLCO held a Workshop "Consumer Protection in the Digital Economy" in Nusa Dua - Bali, Wednesday (09/05/2018). The workshop was opened by ISO COPOLCO Chair, Guillermo Zucal accompanied by Bambang, who revealed that this theme was very actual and relevant considering the current world conditions where consumers make transactions in the digital economy ranging from banking, telecommunications, e-commerce, transportation and others.

4. Conclusions

All ministers of communications and information technology in Southeast Asia agreed to adopt ASEAN ICT Masterplan 2020. The ICT Vision of the Masterplan 2020 is to encourage ASEAN to digital to enable a safe, sustainable and transformative economy, and to enable an innovative, inclusive and integrated ASEAN community. ASEAN ICT Masterplan is fundamental because the leaders of ASEAN countries are aware of the benefits obtained if ICT is one of the important instruments. The impact of ICT Masterplan was also felt in Indonesia, which led to the development and advancement of information and communication technology (ICT) to be very good and felt in almost every aspect of people's lives. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) on digital economic performance has become an interesting issue in the economic field. The role of the digital economy in world economic growth will be increasingly significant. To maximize this potential, the Indonesian government has provided various important things to support Indonesia's economic readiness in the face of the ICT Masterplan 2020, including: the transformation of MSMEs into e-UMKM, Development of local startups in Indonesia, Indonesia digital economic cooperation developed, adequate infrastructure development, development Human resources, as well as Consumer Security and Protection. From these various readiness, Indonesia is declared ready to face ICT Masterplan 2020. The government's strategy is predicted to run effectively until 2020. This research assumption believes that the government's commitment to safeguard and encourage the growth of Indonesia's digital economy is carried out consistently, until 2020, even 2025 to be achieved into a digital economy largest in ASEAN.

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